

A NOVEL APPROACH FOR IMAGERE STORATION USING DEEP LEARNING ALGORITHM**Ananya J A, Bhavana B, Isha Purnesh, Harshitha N Bhat.**Students, Dept of Electronics and Communication Engineering,
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India.**Prof. Padmavathi C**Assistant Professor, Dept of Electronics and Communication Engineering,
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Bangalore, India.**ABSTRACT:**

The Restoration of the image helps greatly in improving the visual quality of images by suppressing noise, blur, and other arti- facts. The application of GANs has become a modern practice in image restoration within recent years. GANs, are a class of deep learning models, which create high quality images by means of generative networks and discriminative networks which differentiates between manufactured and actual pictures or other data.

Keywords:

Image Restoration, Degradation Model, Deblurring, Noise Reduction, Super Resolution

INTRODUCTION:

Blind face restoration aims at recovering high-quality faces from the low-quality counterparts suffering from unknown degradation, such as low-resolution, noise, blur, compression artifacts], etc. When applied to real-world scenarios, it becomes more challenging, due to more complicated degradation, diverse poses and expressions. Previous works typically exploit face-specific priors in face restoration, such as facial landmarks, parsing maps, facial component heat maps, and show that those geometry facial priors are pivotal to recover accurate face shape and details.

OBJECTIVES:

1. Evaluate the effectiveness of GANs in image restoration, focusing on tasks such as noise reduction, de-blurring, and super- resolution, and compare the results with traditional methods.
2. To identify and analyze existing methods for image restoration in GAN to understand their challenges and how to enhance them.

PROBLEMSTATEMENT:

Limited Handling of Complex Image Degradation.
Difficulty in restoring fined details.

SYSTEM DESIGN AND ARCHITECHTURE:

The network architecture incorporates both generator and discriminator models, each of which is paired with specific loss functions. These loss functions are then combined into a list, while the models, along with the associated metrics, are organized within a dictionary-like structure. The complete set of models, loss functions, and metrics is passed to the trainer, which is responsible for managing the training process.

DATA FLOW DIAGRAM:

A Data Flow Diagram(DFD) visually represents the movement of data within a system or process. It

utilizes specific symbols— such as rectangles, circles, and arrows— along with brief text labels to show how data is input, output, stored, and transferred across different components of the system.

Fig:2. dataflow diagram

Face Restoration. Based on general face hallucination, two typical face-specific priors: geometry priors and reference priors, are incorporated to further improve the performance. The geometry priors include facial landmarks face parsing maps and facial component heat maps. However, those priors require estimations from low-quality inputs and inevitably degrades in real-world scenarios. Reference priors usually rely on reference images of the same identity.

Fig:3. Overview of GFP-GAN framework. It consists of a degradation removal module(U-Net)and a pre-trained face GAN as facial prior. They are bridged by a latent code mapping and several Channel-Split Spatial Feature Transform (CS-SFT) layers. During training, we employ 1) intermediate restoration losses to remove complex degradation, 2) Facial component loss with discriminators to enhance facial details, and 3) identity preserving loss to retain face identity.

METHODOLOGY:

Overview of GFP-GAN: GFP-GAN is a face restoration framework that recovers high-quality images from degraded inputs using two core components: a U-Net-based degradation removal module and a pre-trained StyleGAN2 generator.

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Fig:4. Image Restoration using Inpainting Results

IMPLEMENTATION

Training Datasets: To train our GFP-GAN model, we use the FFHQ dataset, which contains 70,000 high-quality face images. All images are resized to $512 \times 512 \times 512$ resolution for training.

Implementation: For our generative facial prior, we use a pre-trained StyleGAN2 model, which generates images at a resolution of $512 \times 512 \times 512$, with the channel multiplier set to one to ensure a compact model size. The mini-batch size is chosen to optimize the training process. Additionally, we focus on a face component loss that targets three key facial areas—the left eye, right eye, and mouth—given their perceptual importance.

Fig:5. Comparison on the CelebA-Test for $\times 4$ face super-resolution.

RESULTS:

Image restoration techniques have seen significant advancements with the rise of deep learning, leading to the development of algorithms designed to tackle challenges such as noise reduction, deblurring, and super-resolution. One such approach is the **Deep Image Prior (DIP)**, which exploits the structure of a convolutional neural network (CNN) to capture image statistics without requiring prior training data.

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Fig 6. Qualitative comparison on the Celeb A-Test for blind face restoration. Our GFP- GAN produces faithful details in mouth and hair. Zoom in for best view

Paper	Methodology	Limitation	Proposed Method
Gong & Zhou[1]	Survey on GANs- Overview of Various GAN architectures and applications.	Requires extensive computational resources; lacks fine grained control over generated details.	Summarized GAN Advancements and suggested Improvements in training methods.
Karras T[4]	Style GAN- Style based Generator for high- quality image synthesis.	Requires extensive computational resources; lacks fine grained control over generated details.	Introduced style-based architecture to improve control over image synthesis.

Table1: Quantitative comparison on CelebA-Test for blind face restoration.

CONCLUSION:

Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) have emerged as a powerful unsupervised learning approach in artificial intelligence, enabling models to generate high-quality data without labeled inputs. Future research can focus on improving model stability, optimizing processing speed for real-time applications, and integrating multi-modal information to enhance restoration performance.

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